

Campus Research Computing Consortium

Professionalization Working Group

2025 Research Computing and Data Workforce Survey Results

Qualitative Analysis Codebook for PEARC26 Short Paper Conference Proceeding
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Description: Parent codes, definitions, and examples from the initial inductive thematic analysis of the CaRCC RCD Professionalization Working Group’s 2025 survey’s free text responses to two questions:

1. *What part of your RCD work do you find most complex? Why?*
 This could relate to technical tasks, interpersonal dynamics, organizational politics, compliance requirements, or something else.
2. *What types of challenges in your RCD Facilitation role require the most effort to manage or resolve? Why?*

Generally, multiple parent codes were allowed per survey response; for clarity, the examples below were taken from responses where only one parent code was assigned.

Code	Definition	Examples
Excluded Responses	Responses excluded from thematic analysis, due to either nonexistent or insubstantial content.	“NA” “no”
Funding Challenges	Responses referring to financial resource constraints and their cascading effects on RCD work. This code captures the direct challenges of obtaining money, and may reference the systemic issues undergirding these challenges.	“Financial issues are a continued challenge and often my role gets cut not for the need, but budgetary concerns.” “Securing consistent funding for RCD projects is a big challenge. Uncertain budgets stall progress and demotivate teams.”
Governance & Compliance Environment	Responses which include the theme of complexities or	“An increased focus on compliance requirements

	<p>challenges arising from navigating regulations, policies, institutional requirements, and legal frameworks. Encompasses references to institutional mechanisms for addressing these challenges, and complexities involved in mapping to systems not designed for evolving compliance landscapes.</p>	<p>without support from a compliance expert.”</p> <p>“I am probably the least comfortable with compliance requirements, so due to legal complexities of the global research that happens here, I think that would be the most complex.”</p>
<p>Knowledge & Capacity Management</p>	<p>Responses that point toward the possibilities and limitations of human cognition and effort in RCD work. This code includes immediate-to-long-term skill-building and capacity themes. Includes references to how RCD work can be limited by what human resources exist given the complex prioritization necessary to sustain effective services.</p>	<p>“Strategic planning, leading and developing workforce.”</p> <p>“Tackling new problems and learning the context of the research and analysis.”</p>
<p>Organizational Structures & Dynamics</p>	<p>Responses which emphasize challenges arising from working within or among institutional frameworks, hierarchies, and bureaucratic systems. Captures how the composition of an organization can itself create friction, disinterest, or counter-incentives to effective RCD work.</p>	<p>“Coordinating, collaborating, and informing of RCD services across the university. We work well with Research Computing, but it's other units within academic departments, office of research (some portions), and general university IT that can be hard to reach.”</p> <p>“I find project management and team coordination most difficult, as we are split into multiple teams working on the same system, but with different roles and priorities.”</p>
<p>Quotable</p>	<p>Responses highlighted as possible quotes to be used in reporting/publication.</p>	<p>“Facilitating these conversations means acting as a “translator,” breaking down jargon to build alignment without oversimplifying technical realities or dismissing research</p>

		<p>needs. This demands not just technical expertise but emotional intelligence to manage frustration or miscommunication.”</p> <p>“Facilitation requires a lot of different skills. The fact that communications, project management, business analysis, and outreach specialist roles are missing and not often acknowledged as valuable and essential roles in our community puts us at a disadvantage. These are often skills that our facilitators need to adopt.”</p>
Research Process Facilitation	Responses which emphasize enabling the research lifecycle from a researcher-centered perspective. This code reflects RCD professionals positioning themselves as partners in research situated at intersecting vectors of feasibility.	<p>“Working with researchers to create new and innovative solutions [to] solve complex problems.”</p> <p>“Figuring out how to empower scientists in their interaction with their IT shops.”</p>
Stakeholder Interface Complexity	Responses which include themes centered on the interpersonal dimensions of RCD work that require emotional intelligence, communication skill, relationship management. Captures the variability and individualization required when working with diverse stakeholders who have different communication styles, priorities, timelines, values, cultural backgrounds, and expectations.	<p>“Negotiating unrealistic expectations, often due to a lack of awareness or unwillingness to engage, and reaching agreement about feasible solutions.”</p> <p>“Interpersonal relationships: because each person’s styles and fields are different.”</p>
Technical Integration Complexity	Responses emphasizing the work of providing bespoke compute stacks for research, as well as other technical-centered concerns, with ever-changing parameters. Encompasses	“Integrations -- gluing together multiple pieces of software I've not necessarily had a role in creating, especially when they don't naturally interface with each other.”

	calibration, troubleshooting, optimization, and maintenance activities.	“One-of-a-kind, non-reproducible bugs due to extremely specialized nature of research software.”
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